

Pedagogical Approaches in the Knowledge Society: The Flipped Classroom Method for the Development of Creativity and Dialogical Learning

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Abstract—Dialogical learning and teamwork have become the principles demanded by the knowledge society, given that we are currently living in a completely globalised world that requires skilled citizens to collaborate on a social, professional and academic level. Likewise, creativity is another key element requested by organisations to solve problems. Against this background, some student-centred teaching methods like flipped classrooms are appearing. Therefore, this paper aimed to analyse the implementation of the flipped classroom method as a factor to develop dialogical learning and creativity. To this regard, a quantitative method was used, applying a survey prepared ad hoc to a sample of 308 students from Spain and Colombia, in order to know whether implementing the flipped classroom truly enhances the development of such skills. According to the results obtained, it is stated that developing the flipped classroom method promotes a team-based work dynamic, which generates dialogical learning among students. It also enhances creativity, since it provides students with autonomy to carry out their tasks. Finally, the flipped classroom pedagogical approach is a teaching method with numerous advantages and benefits for students to adapt to the competencies required by the knowledge society.

Keywords—Flipped Classroom, Dialogical Learning, Creativity, Teaching Methodology, Pedagogical Approach.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the Flipped Classroom methodology is being implemented in the classrooms of different educational levels, which it is defined as the flipped of roles in the classroom, where the student acquires the theoretical knowledge outside and the classroom becomes a propitious space for resolving doubts and cooperative work [1, 2]. Therefore, the student previously works the contents outside the school context from the use of digital tools to develop them later in the classroom.

The flipped classroom teaching method is offered as a key pedagogical approach in this process of change. It began with Bergmann and Sams' [2] concern, who started to record their presentations with audio to offer them as student support material, with the

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